

QSAR modeling of *E. coli* promoters with parameters selected by binary matrix shuffling filter

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Manuscript received online 06 June 2014, revised 01 July 2014, accepted 02 July 2014

Abstract : The 1123 topological structure parameters of DNA bases were directly used as descriptors to characterize the sequence of 38 *E. coli* promoters. For the correspondingly generated high-dimensional feature set, the correlation analysis and binary matrix shuffling filter (BMSF) were successively used to remove the redundancy or useless features, and only 20 features were finally reserved, with definite meanings. Based on reserved features and support vector regression (SVR), a quantitative structure-activity relationship (QSAR) model was established for the analysis of 38 *E. coli* promoters, and the leave-one-out (LOO) prediction accuracy of this model was of 0.838, superior to that of reference model, i.e. partial least squares (PLS). Referring to the SVR interpretation system, the established QSAR model in this work has extremely significant nonlinear regression, and the relationship between real promoter strength and 11 significant reserved features was directly given out. This work provides an efficient tool for the QSAR analysis of promoters and other similar molecular sequences.

Keywords : Quantitative sequence-activity model, feature selection, support vector regression, promoter.

Introduction

As a hub for the transfer and expression of gene information, the genetic transcription is one of the most important links for the regulation of gene expression. Among this process, the promoter is a key element to determine the start site and frequency of transcription¹. And the strength of promoter will affect many aspects of transcription, including the initial combination degree between promoter and RNA polymerase, the support efficiency for isomerization, and the complexity of polymerase to escape from binding site, etc.^{2,3}. Extensive studies have been successively conducted to research the relationships between the promoter sequences and their strengths from the 1980s⁴⁻⁷. These studies have found uncovered that the promoters located closer to the consensus sequences have stronger activities. However, there was short of the precise quantitative description on determination of the functional strength of some DNA sequence

fragments.

In recent years, quantitative structure-activity relationship (QSAR) has been commonly used to study the relationship between the bio-macromolecule properties and their physiological activates⁸⁻¹⁰. To predict the strength of *E. coli* promoter, Mulligan *et al.*⁵ and Jonsson *et al.*¹¹ have firstly characterized the sequences of *E. coli* promoter and lysogenization and then, established the regression model to compute their strength, which obtained the relatively satisfying results. The prediction accuracy of QSAR model is mainly related to the descriptor extraction, feature selection, and basic model method. The descriptor should be efficient to characterize the molecular structure and are easy to be obtained. Generally, the characterization of bio-macromolecule often leads to a problem of high-dimensional features, which has adverse effect on further modeling. Hasegawa *et al.* have verified that the genetic algorithm-based partial least squares (GA-

PLS) method can enhance prediction and interpretation of the QSAR analysis of human immuno-deficiency virus type I (HIV-1) protease inhibitors¹². Zhang *et al.* have proposed a novel method named binary matrix shuffling filter (BMSF) to select informative genes from high-dimension feature set, and made a satisfying results for the recognition of cancer oncogenes¹³. For the basic regression modeling method, the traditional empirical risk minimization (EMR) based modeling methods including multiple linear regression (MLR), principal component regression (PCR), partial least square regression (PLS) and artificial neural networks (ANN) has many defects¹⁴⁻¹⁷, which cannot obtain satisfied high-performance regression model for high dimensional features with small sample size dataset. As a novel realization of statistic learning theory, support vector machine (SVM) is one of the fastest growing machine learning methods¹⁵. In the basis on the minimum structure risk principle, SVM can better solve the problems of small sample size, non-linearity, over-fitting, dimension disaster, local minima, etc., which is suited for the QSAR modeling for promoter strength.

Based on the DNA primary sequence, this work used the 1123 topological structure parameters of each kind of DNA bases to characterize the promoter sequence. The correlation analysis between the generated features and promoter strength was conducted to select the significant features with corresponding *P* values less than 0.001 and then, BMSE method was used for the nonlinear screening of the initially reserved features to obtain the optimal feature subset. Based on reserved features and SVR, the QSAR model was established for analysis of 38 *Escherichia coli* promoters.

Methods and materials :

Data set :

The promoter plays an important role in gene expression. Compared with eukaryotic promoters, prokaryotic promoters have simpler structure and are easy to be identified. Considering that *Escherichia coli* (*E. coli*) is one of the most widely used model organisms in the field of human health, this work selected 38 *E. coli* promoter sequences⁹ for further QSAR analysis. Except for the original *E. coli* promoters, this data set also contains several recomposed promoters deriving from the promoters infected by λ bacteriophage. The lengths of all 38 pro-

motor sequences are of 68bp (-49 region ~ +19 region), and each sequence contains Sextama box (-35 region), Pribnow box (-10 region), and transcriptional start site. The strength of promoters is expressed as the logarithm of P_{bla} -units.

Characterization of promoter sequence :

The 1123 topological structure parameters derived from Virtual Computational Chemistry Laboratory (<http://www.vcclab.org/lab/pclient/start.html>) are a relatively comprehensive summary for each DNA base (A, G, C, T), with a definite meaning. This work directly used these 1123 topological structure parameters as descriptors to characterize the sequence structures of *E. coli* promoter.

Each DNA base in each promoter sequence was characterized by 1123 topological structure parameters derived from Virtual Computational Chemistry Laboratory (named as DB1123), and the generated descriptors were arranged in a tandem order. The thirty-eight *E. coli* promoters used in this study were all equaling sequences consist of 68 DNA bases. Through the replacement of each DNA base with corresponding DB1123 parameter, in total, 76364 (1123 \times 68) descriptors were finally generated for each promoter sequence. This high-dimensional features set will inevitably cause the dimensionality curse for regression modeling, and the redundancy or useless information may exist among these features. Hence, the selection of generated high-dimensional features is extremely essential before modeling.

Feature selection :

Initial selection based on correlation analysis :

The generated 76364 features (descriptors) were combined with the strength value of promoters to compose a data set D. The correlation analysis was conducted for data set D, and only significant features ($P < 0.001$) were reserved for further modeling. This initial selection process can efficiently reduce the feature dimensions.

Rapid and nonlinear selection for high-dimensional features based on Binary Matrix Shuffling Filter (BMSF) :

On the basis of support vector classification (SVC), Zhang *et al.* have proposed a novel feature selection method binary matrix shuffling filter (BMSF) to rapidly screen redundancy genes for nine cancer gene expression datasets with high-dimensional features¹³. By replacing

the support vector classification in the BMSF algorithm with support vector regression (SVR), this work learned from the core algorithm of BMSF method to select the generated high-dimensional features using DB1123 parameter for the characterization of *E. coli* promoters.

Suppose the original training set is consist of n -dimensional vector Y and $n \times m$ -dimensional matrix X , where Y are the promoter strength values $\log P_{\text{bla}}$ -units and X are initial reserved features obtained by correlation analysis. Firstly, a $k \times m$ -dimensional matrix M compose of 1 and 0 is randomly generated, and limiting condition is that the number of 0 and 1 in each column should be in balance, k is the given number of combinations determined by the size of m values and the expending time for each round selection, and the initial k value is sets as 500 and will decreases with the step of 50 for each round selection, and the lower limit is set as 200 in this work. A MSE value could be obtained through cross-validation based SVR (unless otherwise specified, this work adopts 5-fold cross validation, and kernel function was set as radial basis function). Then, k MSE values would be obtained by repeating the above step.

Secondly, a new training set is constructed with those k MSE values (dependent variables) and matrix M (independent variable). For each column of the $k \times m$ matrix M , the element values are replaced to produce two groups of test sets with all the elements of 0 and 1, keeping the elements of other columns unchanged. The predictions with SVR are conducted for these two test set, and the corresponding MSE_0 and MSE_1 can be obtained. Comparing the mean values of k MSE_0 and MSE_1 , if the mean value of MSE_0 is less than that of MSE_1 , the feature corresponding to this column is excluded from the given feature set. Otherwise, this feature is included. By repeating this step, we obtained the preserved features for one round of selection. Repeating this process, the high-dimensional features were screened for multiple rounds until no features could be deleted anymore.

The reserved features are used for further QSAR modeling.

Modeling method and reference models :

The software LIBSVM¹⁸ was adopted as a concrete realization of SVM in this study. And the nonlinear radial basis function was selected as kernel function due to

its optimal generalization ability in most data sets.

The reference models were multiple linear regressions (MLR) and partial least square (PLS). MLR needs two or more factors as independent variables to explain the change of dependent variables, and the relations between independent and dependent variables are linear. PLS integrates the excellences of principal component analysis, canonical correlation analysis and multivariate regression analysis, which can well solve the problem that the model has poor accuracy when the sample number is less than feature number. The PLS method can guarantee the maximum correlation between the extracted features and dependent variables, on the basis of extracting more independent information as far as possible. The algorithms of MLR and PLS were realized through invoking the functions in Matlab 2013a.

As the reference feature selection method, the GA-PLS algorithm toolbox developed by Leardi¹⁹ was used to select the most suitable set of generated features for regression model.

Model evaluation and interpretation :

On account of the limited data samples, this work employed the leave one out (LOO) cross validation to evaluate the model performance.

The evaluation indices Q^2 and root-mean-square error (RMSE) were used to measure the predictive ability of the model, which are defined as :

$$Q^2 = 1 - \frac{\sum_{i=1}^n (y_i - \hat{y}_i)^2}{\sum_{i=1}^n (y_i - \bar{y})^2} \quad (1)$$

$$\text{RMSE} = \sqrt{\sum_{i=1}^n (y_i - \hat{y}_i)^2 / n} \quad (2)$$

where y_i is the experimental activity value of the i -th sample while \hat{y}_i is the predictive value, and \bar{y} is the mean of the experimental values of all samples, and n is the sample size.

Without an explicit expression, SVR has poor interpretation for regression modeling. Referring to the interpretation system established for SVR in our previous

study²⁰, this work conducted the significance tests of model, single-factor importance analysis, and single-factor effects analysis to improve the interpretation of proposed SVR model.

Results and discussion

Descriptor selection and comparison of regression models :

There are 76364 descriptors generated for the characterization of each *E. coli* promoter sequence, using DB1123 parameters. This work conducted a correlation analysis on these descriptors to retain the descriptors having statistical significance ($P < 0.001$). Then, the BMSF and GA-PLS methods were used for further selection, and only 20 and 14 features were finally reserved, respectively. With the features before and after the selections, the QSAR models were established based on MLR, PLS and SVM. From Table 1, among the three models established with the reserved features after initial selection, PLS model has the best accuracy. After the selection of GA-PLS, the prediction performances of each model are largely improved. However, after the selection of BMSF, each model has further improvement in prediction performances. By comparison, the SVM model combined with BMSF has the best prediction results among all the models. Conclusion can be drawn that the feature selection can not only reduce the feature number and remove the redundancy information, but also improve the prediction performance. To compare the merits of feature selection methods BMSF and GA-PLS, the experimental

Table 1. Comparison of different models on *E. coli* promoter dataset

FS method	Models	A^a	N^b	Q^2	RMSE
All descriptors	MLR	–	5679	–0.043	0.468
	PLS	8	5679	0.662	0.267
	SVM	–	5679	0.399	0.356
GA-PLS	MLR	–	14	0.666	0.265
	PLS	4	14	0.793	0.209
	SVM	–	14	0.744	0.232
BMSF	MLR	–	20	0.734	0.237
	PLS	3	20	0.822	0.194
	SVM	–	20	0.838	0.185

^aNumbers of latent variables; ^bNumbers of descriptors.

versus predicted strengths of 38 *E. coli* promoters for each model are shown in Fig. 1. We can see that the circle symbols for BMSF are closest points to the diagonal in each sub-figure, which indicate that the BMSF algorithm has better universality than GS-PLS for different modeling methods.

Model interpretation for SVM :

Referring to the interpretation system proposed for SVM regression modeling²⁴, the F values is calculated as 8.287 for SVM model established for QSAR analysis of *E. coli* promoters in this work, which indicates that the nonlinear regression of SVM model is of extreme significance ($F_{0.01}(20, 17) = 3.162$). The significance test of importance for a single factor shows that the relative importance of two reserved descriptors reached extremely significant levels and nine reached significance, and Table

Fig. 1a. Experimental versus predicted strengths of 38 *E. coli* promoters for SVR model.

Table 2. The description and *F* value of DIRECT significant factors

No.	Position	Des ID ^a	Description	<i>F</i> -value
1	-21	IDDM	Mean information content on the distance degree magnitude	15.384**
2	-26	H4u	H autocorrelation of lag 4/unweighted	8.913**
3	+15	X0sol	Solvation connectivity index chi-0	7.429*
4	-4	QW	Quasi-Wiener index (Kirchhoff number)	7.378*
5	+14	Vp	V total size index/weighted by atomic polarizabilities	6.440*
6	+16	X3v	Valence connectivity index chi-3	5.878*
7	-22	HOMA	Harmonic Oscillator Model of Aromaticity index	5.285*
8	+16	X3Av	Average valence connectivity index chi-3	5.151*
9	+8	SP04	Shape profile no. 04	5.033*
10	-40	DP06	Molecular profile no. 06	4.722*
11	+8	SIC5	Structural information content (neighborhood symmetry of 5-order)	4.468*

^aDescription ID in VCCLAB website. **: $P = 0.01$, $F_{0.01}(1, 17) = 8.4$; *: $P = 0.05$, $F_{0.05}(1, 17) = 4.451$.

Fig. 1b. Experimental versus predicted strengths of 38 *E. coli* promoters for PLS model.

Fig. 1c. Experimental versus predicted strengths of 38 *E. coli* promoters for MLR model.

Fig. 2. The single-factor effects of marked features characterized by DIRECT.

2 lists their relative orders of importance and corresponding F values of these eleven descriptors. The single-factor effects of eleven significant descriptors are shown in Fig. 2, as can be observed, the strength of *E. coli* promoters increased with increasing values of descriptors No. 8, 9 and 11, specially, the No. 9 and 11 are belonging to the position +8 in the promoter sequences, which indicates that the variety of bases in this position may influence significantly the strength of *E. coli* promoters. The strength value decreased with increasing values of No. 2, 3, 4, 5, 6 and 7, among these reserved descriptors, the No. 3, 5 and 6 are distributed in the neighboring of position +14, which demonstrate that variation of the descriptors in these positions has a significant association with the strength of promoter.

Conclusions

The 1123 topological structure parameters derived from Virtual Computational Chemistry Laboratory was directly used as descriptor to characterize the sequence structures of *E. coli* promoter. For the correspondingly generated high-dimensional features, i.e. 76364 features for each *E. coli* promoter sequence (68bp), the correlation analysis was firstly conducted for initial feature selection and then, the BMSF and GA-PLS methods were used to conduct the subtle screening for the reserved features after initial selection to obtain two optimal feature subsets. With the reserved features before and after the subtle selec-

tion, the MLR, PLS and SVM models were established for QSAR analysis of *E. coli* promoters. The results show that a large number of useless or redundant features can be successively removed after selection, and the SVR model combined with BMSF made the best performance. Referring to the SVR interpretation system, this work also found that the strength of *E. coli* promoters has remarkable correlations with some certain properties of DNA bases located in the specific region of promoter sequence. This work provides a reference for the identification of promoter and the determination of its strength.

Acknowledgements

The research was supported by a grant from the National Natural Science Foundation of China (No. 61300130), the Doctoral Foundation of Ministry of Education of China (No. 20124320110002) and the Postdoctoral Science Foundation of Hunan Province (No. 2012RS4039).

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